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IMPROVING PERSONNEL MOTIVATION AT AN ENTERPRISE IN THE PANDEMIC CONDITIONS

УДОСКОНАЛЕННЯ МОТИВАЦІЇ ПЕРСОНАЛУ НА ПІДПРИЄМСТВІ В УМОВАХ ПАНДЕМІЇ

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Продіус О.І., Свищ А.В., Відал Агіналдо Де Лукас. Удосконалення мотивації персоналу на підприємстві в умовах пандемії. Оглядова стаття.

Стаття присвячена проблемам управління персоналу та особливостей функції мотивації в управлінні персоналом в умовах пандемії. Розглянуто сутність мотивації праці, досліджено шляхи підсилення конкурентоспроможності підприємства за рахунок підвищення мотивації персоналу до праці у контексті сучасної системи управління персоналом. Доведено, що ефективність і якість управління людськими ресурсами в умовах пандемії набувають все більш важливого значення як фактор розвитку та конкурентоспроможності підприємства.

Запропоновано ключові напрями мотивації персоналу підприємств в умовах пандемії, які вимагають не тільки інших підходів, ніж у допандемічні часи, але й емпатії, турботи та уваги до ментального здоров'я, що дозволить зберегти висококваліфікованих співробітників у контексті підвищення конкурентоспроможності підприємства в умовах невизначеності.

Ключові слова: мотивація, персонал, управління персоналом, система мотивації праці персоналу, розвиток, кадрова служба, підприємство, мотиваційний механізм, стимулювання, пандемія COVID-19

Prodius O.I., Svyshch A.V., Vidal Aguinaldo De Lucas. Improving Personnel Motivation at an Enterprise in the Pandemic Conditions. Review article.

The article is dedicated to the problems of personnel management and features of the motivation function in personnel management in the pandemic conditions. The essence of work motivation has been considered, the ways of strengthening an enterprise competitiveness by increasing the personnel motivation to work in the context of modern personnel management system have been investigated. It has been proved that the efficiency and quality of human resource management in a pandemic are becoming increasingly important as a factor in the enterprise development and competitiveness.

The key areas of motivation of the enterprise personnel in the pandemic have been proposed, which require not only other approaches than in the pre-pandemic times, but also empathy, care and attention to mental health, which will retain highly qualified employees in the context of increasing competitiveness in uncertainty

Keywords: motivation, personnel, personnel management, personnel motivation system, development, personnel service, enterprise, motivational mechanism, incentives, the COVID-19 pandemic

The realities of today make their corrections both in our lives and in the work of enterprises, whose management performs all anti-epidemic measures, which have been introduced in the territory of one or another city of Ukraine in connection with the spread of coronavirus disease COVID-19. All the enterprises were forced to take measures to prevent the spread of the infection, such as: the termination of any mass events at the enterprise, the control over using the individual protection means by employees, the transfer of part or all employees to remote work, etc.

The problem of personnel motivation became especially acute during the pandemic, when quarantine was introduced in the country, and many entrepreneurs were forced to limit the activities of their enterprises. Improving the personnel motivation system at the enterprises is a priority task, as one of the problems of personnel management is rational use of human factor, and this is possible only in an effective approach to the motivation system. The lack of research, development and discussion and the need to solve certain problems related to personnel management in the pandemic conditions and their degree of influence on the results of the enterprises activity, both in economic science and in production practice, have determined the need for further consideration and selection of the main directions of the study.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Many scientists devoted their studies to the consideration of personnel motivation issues, among whom one can mention such scientists as

L. Balabanova, V. Brych, L. Bondarchuk, O. Budiakova, M. Denysenko, N. Nikolaichuk, L. Hromko, S. Filyppova etc. At this stage many scientists investigate the motivation mechanism of personnel management in their works. A. Lobza, I. Guz form the motivation mechanism as a complex system of different ways of influence on the personnel of the organization [5, p.511]. S. Kravchenko and A. Korneva emphasize that the motivation mechanism should be formed taking into account the needs, interests, peculiarities of employees' behavior [3, p.286]. The concept "motivation mechanism in the enterprise personnel management" is interpreted in this work as a combination of principles, methods, tools and directions, oriented on satisfaction of the employees' needs and the personnel potential preservation of the enterprise. A.O. Klimchuk considers motivational mechanisms on the example of the enterprise, shows the degree of interrelation between indicators of salary, including bonuses, employees turnover, satisfaction of personnel with conditions and labor results [2, p.12]. V. Korolov considers practical experience of using mechanisms of trade stimulation and operational personnel on the example of "Silpo" trading network [4, p.88]. A significant contribution to the study of work motivation was made by D. Bohynia, O. Grishnova, G. Zavinovska, who studied the essence of work motivation in the context of enterprise personnel management. Such scientists as Y. Zavadskiy, L. Chervinska, V. Shynkarenko, O. Kryvoruchko studied the work motivation and its impact on the enterprise results. In their works experts consider motivation as a tool for ensuring the enterprise effective activity. Both domestic and foreign scientists, such as Yu. Zaitsev, O. Krasnonosova, I. Kravchuk and others pay their main attention to problems of material stimulation. Such scientists as M. Armstrong, I. Ansoff, H. Dessler, V. Hrynova, A. Zut, A. Kibanov, H. Lych, H. Nazarova, O. Yastremska, A. Tkachenko and others devoted their works to the problems of personnel management. In turn, the research of strategic aspects of employee development is covered in the works of such authors as V. Verkhohliadova, A. Kolot, Yu. Lysenko, Yu. Odehov, V. Savchenko, V. Spivak, A. Topmson. Strategic personnel management was considered by such scientists and practices as: L. Batchenko, V. Honcharov, O. Novikova, H. Osovskaya, I. Prodius, M. Prokopenko, S. Filyppova, H. Tarasenko, O. Umanskyi etc. The works of scientists-economists P. Borshchevskiy, H. Viechkanova, V. Hrynova, M. Horielov, Yu. Krasnov, A. Kolot, O. Martiakova, I. Maslova, O. Moroz, O. Rudchenko are devoted to improving the quality of the production process on the basis of effective use of the human factor.

Both Ukrainian and foreign scientists, in particular A. Afonin, O. Bohutskiy, I. Bieliaieva, F. Herzberg, S. Dovbnia, G. Emerson, Y. Zavadskiy, D. Karnegy, A. Kolot, K. Levin, E. Louter, A. Maslow, D. McGregor, L. Porter, F. Taylor, F. Khmil, A. Chukhn and others devoted their works to the theoretical development of the issues related to employees' motivation,

stimulation and the approaches formation to increase labour productivity.

Despite the considerable scientific order of the above mentioned authors, it is possible to emphasize that in the domestic and foreign literature remain insufficiently considered questions connected with motivation mechanism improvement in accordance with changing conditions of functioning of Ukrainian enterprises, particular during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The main part

In modern economic conditions there are different approaches to personnel management, the difference of which is based on different attitude to personnel as to the management object. In the first approach employees are not considered as people, as a management object is considered only the operational function, i.e. work (K. Marx, F. Taylor). The second approach is based on the recognized personnel of the organization as an independent management object. Two concepts can be called as part of this approach: The Concept of Personnel Management and the Concept of Human Resources Management. The Concept of Personnel Management considers employees because of their role, i.e. positions in production (Jh. Watson, T. Berne, G.M. Stalker, L.S. Lor). In the concept of human resources management is shifting focus from position to person as a complex object of organization (A. Maslow, F. Herzberg, D. McGregor and others). The third approach considers personnel as a complex and managed resource of the organization or the organization capital (T. Shultz, G. Becker and their followers).

The modern stage of theories development of human resources management is accepted to be related to the theory of "business management", in which a person began to be considered as a source of competitive advantages achievement. Thus, one of the important directions of forming the effective management system of the enterprise in the conditions of dynamic changes of the environment is the constructing and using an effective mechanism of enterprise personnel motivation using accumulated world experience. Creating an effective system of employees' motivation at the enterprise is an important task for each manager, because it directly influences the labour force productivity, and the enterprise productivity depends on profitability and competitiveness of the enterprise.

Under the pandemic conditions and limited financial resources enterprises in different sectors of the Ukrainian economy are looking for ways to strengthen the enterprises competitiveness by increasing the personnel motivation to work and creating an effective system of personnel management capable to influence the personnel behaviour, directing it to more productive work, achievement of competitive labour results and goals of the enterprise in the conditions of dynamic changes of the environment.

Motivation forms the process of a person's personal psychological state, which determines the behaviour,

creates activity and motivates it. On the other hand, motivation is a desire of an employee to satisfy his/her needs, that is, a combination of internal and external forces, which motivate the person to work and give him/her an aim to achieve certain goals [10].

Motivation as an internal, not always conscious factor, defines the direction of the employee's activity and acts as a leading managerial function. Knowing the peculiarities of the employees' motivation simplifies the management process and contributes to the increase of professional activity efficiency [8].

Motivation is to encourage the employee to work useful for the organization in which he works. It is obvious that for effective carrying out of motivational measures it is necessary to understand what exactly the motivation for the employee is, and how to properly direct these motives in a mainstream useful for the organization [10].

An effective system of wages is a guarantee of stability, reduces the turnover of personnel, ensures high quality of tasks performance, helps to attract highly qualified and experienced employees, and thus ensures success of the enterprise in the strategic dimension.

The factor that ensures such efficiency of economic activity is labour motivation as a factor of improving the efficiency and productivity of labour, increasing the efficiency of realization of accumulated labour potential motivation for hired workers influences stability of highly skilled labour collectives, increasing labour productivity, moral and material condition of each employee and the personnel in general [6].

As the study of scientific literature shows, motivation is understood a set of conditions or motives that influence the person's behaviour, which direct his activity in the necessary for the organization, regulating the intensity of work, labour, which encourage to reveal diligence, persistence, diligence in achieving goals. In other words, it is the driving force that helps the employee combine all his/her efforts and effectively fulfill his responsibilities to achieve the set goal.

Personnel motivation includes a combination of incentives that determine the quality of the employee's work in the company. These incentives are divided into two main groups: economic and non-economic. The latter are divided into organizational and moral. Economic incentives include a direct economic reward consisting of payments received by the employee in the form of wages, salaries, bonuses and incentives; indirect benefits that cover all the benefits, including life and health insurance, social assistance such as benefits (pension insurance, medical insurance, educational assistance). Non-economic incentives are based on satisfaction of something, for example, from the work itself, for example, extraordinary orders execution, service promotion. Most scientists and organizations view labour remuneration as the main tool for the workforce motivation. At the same time, most organizations do not use modern labour remuneration systems, including grading. In case the amount of employees' remuneration is considered to be worthy, does not give motivation to the personnel.

Then the leading role of motivation goes to non-economic incentives. On the other hand, under the conditions of constant stress, psychological pressure, deterioration of the social and psychological climate, the role of non-economic incentives is also growing. As it has been noted, the spread of coronavirus infection has significantly affected the employees' morale. Therefore, the main incentives for staff motivation in a pandemic are called non-economic. The pandemic began with the announcement of non-working days and the transfer of a significant number of workers to remote work. As a result of research by ABD architects it was found that most of the translated workers (66,5%) had never worked from home before, 24.6% – 1-2 times a week, 5.1% – 34 times a week and only 3,1% - all the time. The efficiency of work at home and in the office was also assessed.

According to the results, it is possible to reach an uncomfortable conclusion that the work on the "remote" was less effective than in the office. The survey results showed that 78% of employees saw shortcomings in "distance" and only 18.3% of respondents noted an increase in their productivity. To the shortcomings mentioned in the study, we will also add an increase in the amount of work performed. This is due, in particular, to the fact that the person performs work alone and the responsibility for the content and quality of its work is considerably increased. As it has already been emphasized, the COVID-19 pandemic forced some employees to work from home, which raised the motivation issue of the remote workforce. When employees work from home, their activities require coordination and control over the performance of their duties, so standard motivation methods that increase financial interest will not produce the desired result.

When considering the characteristics of personnel motivation during coronavirus infection one cannot ignore the problem of the impact of internal incentives on the motivational behavior of staff. The observations showed that many people tried to make their position in organizations more stable, to protect themselves from dismissal, to transfer to lower-paid work and showed an initiative in search of effective forms of their work in conditions of remote work. This was especially true for workers in industries where the level of wages was lower than the average: culture and art, education, physical culture, social security, service sectors.

In general, based on the study of scientific literature and analysis of practical material, we can identify the following aspects of personnel motivation in the pandemic conditions: awareness of the importance of work performed both socially and organizationally and personally; new competencies development; management's concern for personnel, economic and non-economic assistance to employees in difficult life situations; flexible work schedule; awareness and demonstration of the health value, voluntary health insurance; control over employees' activities by employees themselves during the implementation of related business processes. Thus, one can come to the disappointing conclusion that a manager always needs to encourage employees to work.

Personnel motivation is a multi-faceted process that allows employees to take personal needs into account and to meet expectations from their professional activities by achieving goals that must match the goals and objectives of the company, as well as a set of measures taken to improve the employees' productivity and efficiency. Motivation and stimulation of labour activity are important for high productivity and quality of work performed.

In the crisis caused by the pandemic, it is important for the employees to understand how the employers really care about them: whether they think about their safety or are ready to support them in an uncertain situation. The enterprises that demonstrated high social responsibility were able to overcome economic difficulties and remain competitive in an unstable environment. Companies that will be able to respond to the employees' fears and concerns on a regular basis will have competitive advantages. This is the level of care about the employees' physical and moral condition, attitude to vaccination, technology of the office support in hygiene and order, assistance in technical equipment of home offices. Everything related to hygiene and health will become the main motivation factors. Team work will be supported by technical means such as unified bases, boards, clear communications, joint development of group norms and rules. The most important motivating factor will be the employees' participation in the creating the rules and norms of the future working space. Open discussions about problems, reasons for choosing a solution will become important motivational factors that influence the decision to stay in the company and to work productively. Management should be prepared to interact with employees and change tactics, if necessary. Many decisions will have to be made together, and for many managers it will be a huge test.

The workplace transformation will make companies realize that working at home can be effective when it is done voluntarily and for certain categories of personnel not every day. The research has shown that the main problems of the employees who are in the remote are: 23% – have the impossibility of switching the working/home mode; 19% – have feeling of isolation and loneliness; 17% – are emotional negative due to incomplete communications. In the next 6-12 months, employers will face problems such as increased emotional degree, conflicts, claims to work, claims to work schedules, and even physical fatigue within a short period of time after the employees are in office. Companies that can deal with these problems as quickly as possible will benefit from the loyalty and loyalty of personnel, while ignoring these problems will inevitably lead to the burning and loss of effective and valuable employees [13-16].

Thus, creation of an effective system of personnel motivation is an important task for each manager, because it directly influences the workforce productivity, and productivity of the enterprise depends on profitability and competitiveness of the enterprise. Therefore, the main task of work motivation is formation of the desire of employees to work even

better in order to get better results, and accordingly a certain reward for it [9].

The personnel motivation system is one of the important elements of both the personnel management system in the organization and the security system of the enterprise. A well-designed motivation system allows not only to increase human potential in achieving the set goal, but also to bring satisfaction of the employee in the process of work, satisfying their needs and providing safe conditions for the whole enterprise activity [7].

In the complex of anti-crisis measures to motivate the personnel, the work focuses on two main tasks: stabilization of staff and changing the system of material motivation. In the conditions of budget constraints, reducing personnel costs by reducing salaries and bonuses, special attention is needed to instruments of non-material motivation [8].

In order to implement a modern system of personnel motivation at the enterprise it is necessary to consider already existing, to reveal its weak and strong sides. It is only possible to bring into operation an organized system of motivation for getting the necessary result by some influence of the governing body or person. Some tools are needed to influence the elements of the motivation system so that it can begin its functioning. In order to move effectively to meet the goal, the enterprise management should not only plan and organize work, but also apply the system of motivation to employees according to the plan to achieve the goals of the enterprise. An effective motivation system for the enterprise employees is very important for implementation of personnel policy, providing a basis for many procedures: internal movement, promotion, remuneration, moral stimulation, etc.

Employees' motivation of is the increase of work efficiency at the enterprise in general and therefore is one of the main tasks of management. The factor that will help to make the motivation system universal may be the approach to active personnel policy and the components development of a targeted motivation system.

According to the results of the research conducted by HR portal hh.ua, several popular reasons of companies employees were formed in the Ukrainian labour market (Fig. 1) [10].

So, as we can see, the first place is career growth (39%), supporters of a good team and recognition of colleagues and management make up 29% and 28% respectively. Also one of the important motivators is flexible work hours (27%). Corporate culture (9%) and corporate social responsibility (6%) play a minor role in the personnel motivation. The reasons that prevent the creation of an effective team are the personnel turnover at the enterprise. It also negatively affects the enterprise corporate culture. The complex influence of factors causing the change requires a complex of actions to reduce the personnel turnover at the enterprise. Salary at the company consists of rates and bonuses. Analysis of the payment system shows that it is quite effective for both employees and the company.

Figure 1. Main Non-Material Motivators of Employees, %

Source: compiled by authors on materials [10].

The enterprise strives to assess the share of each employee's contribution to the development and achievement of the company goals. Employees have a goal of achieving high results, which allows them to get more bonuses. But, unfortunately, there are significant shortcomings in this payment system, i.e. low basic salary and low interest from the work performed, which is added to the bonus part of the salary.

In order to motivate the enterprise employees the enterprise management considers the issue of increasing the wages. Because for the majority of employees it is the financial stability that is the main need in difficult times. But it is dangerous for an enterprise to simply increase the employees' salary if it is not connected with the performance indicators of their activity. It is proposed to increase the percentage of bonuses for the performed work, as well as for overfulfillment of the established performance indicators. Thus, an effective method for the personnel motivation by the wages at the enterprise will be used. Increasing the financial component will increase competition in the employers' market, but not employees.

Complex relations with employees are also one of the reasons for personnel turnover at the enterprise. Conflict situations that arise between employees can significantly worsen the psychological climate in the team and reduce the activities effectiveness.

An urgent need of Ukrainian enterprises is the development of using the personnel corporate ethics code. In order to solve this problem, experts recommend that the enterprise should increase the level of employee cohesion by holding various corporate events. Using socio-psychological methods of employees motivation will help to solve the problem of effective motivation. To encourage the effective work of employees, the enterprise is obliged to develop a compensation package, which includes a set of tangible and intangible benefits received by employees from the enterprise depending on their contribution.

The enterprise compensation package includes three components – salary, bonuses, non-monetary awards, etc. The main goals of the enterprise compensation package are: increasing labour

productivity; forming involvement, commitment and loyalty to the enterprise, employees' satisfaction; labour market competitiveness, attracting of qualified personnel to the enterprise. Let's consider the structure of the compensation package of the enterprise:

- internal compensation, i.e. satisfaction and prospects that the employee receives from the work itself (participation in decision-making, independence in work, interesting work, opportunities for professional growth, activities diversity, responsibility). Internal compensation which include:
 - direct payments (basic financial compensation), i.e. payment provided in the form of basic salary, holiday and overtime pay, bonuses and commission payments;
 - indirect compensation, benefits (additional and social compensation):
 - indirect payments (indirect financial compensation), i.e. financial compensation not included in direct payments (social protection programmes; medical and other insurance; services and accidental profit; non-cash payment; material support of employees (loans; financial payments from different family circumstances, e.g. birth of a child, etc.); travel in public transport, allowances etc);
 - non-financial compensation (welfare benefits), i.e. additional benefits that the employee receives together with the financial reward from the organization (direct: gratitude, letters, photographs on the board of honour, personal greetings, promotion on the service, etc.) indirect: individual workplace, office, prestigious office furniture, designated place for the car parking, individual mode for work and rest, personal secretary etc.).

Thus, an effective system of employees' motivation is very important for the implementation of personnel policy, providing a basis for many procedures: internal relocation, promotion, remuneration, moral incentives, etc.

It should be noted that when creating a motivation system at the enterprise, using certain types of both material and moral incentives becomes relevant. The

basis of material and moral incentives should be an objective criterion for evaluating the activities of each employee at the enterprise. Motivation system development aimed at meeting the needs of the enterprise employees can be created according to what they consider important, it can cause more favourable conditions for achievement of goals of the organization. Due to the fact that the incentives object is employees of different categories, it is necessary to take into account the difference in their promotion. Career growth and success in life are important for young people. Employees before retirement have strong motives to increase their efficiency, recognition of their authority, values, necessity for the company and so on. For people whose financial situation is quite prosperous, moral motives can be much more important than material ones. Such employees attach great importance to the work content, they enjoy the work and the results achieved. The difficult financial situation determines the predominance of material motives over moral motives. Therefore, the ability to distinguish the employees' needs is the basis for the employees' active behaviour formation and achieve the main goal of the company, i.e. profit maximization [7].

In order to move effectively to meet the goal, the enterprise management should not only plan and organize work, but also apply a motivation system to employees according to the plan to achieve the enterprise goals. Therefore, the enterprise management and specialists in work with the personnel developed the plan of measures on personnel motivation improvement at the enterprises.

The main proposals for improving the system of moral and material incentives for the enterprise personnel are as follows:

- it is necessary to change the organizational and managerial structure for the departments

- reorganization and the introducing innovation management;
- it is necessary to improve the system of training and retraining of enterprise personnel for developing a lifelong learning system;
- it is necessary to expand forms of material incentives for improving material motivation through the bonuses introduction (for initiative, personal contribution to the production process, development and implementation of new equipment and technology), participation in the distribution of economic effects and profits, bonuses;
- it is necessary to increase the role of intangible incentives for improving intangible motivation through the implementation of social programmes and differentiated motivational priorities (based on the definition of individual needs and motives of staff),
- it is necessary to create favourable social and psychological conditions at the enterprise for creating an atmosphere of professional self-development and self-realization, corporate culture strategy, career growth;
- it is necessary to promote motivation to develop corporate culture for taking measures to feel a sense of belonging to the company, to participate in making important decisions; organization of holidays and special events for employees; annual vouchers for employees of sanatoriums, medical institutions and health resorts; providing the personnel with the opportunity to participate in conferences at the regional and national levels; employees motivation who offer new solutions to business problems.

The table 1 shows the measures plan for improving the personnel motivation at the enterprise.

Table 1. The Measures Plan for Improving the Personnel Motivation at the Enterprise

No.	The name and content of the proposed event	Implementation deadlines and periodicity	Responsible person, main performers	Expected result from implementation
1	2	3	4	5
1	Changing organizational and administrative structure, i.e. units reorganization	first quarter	General director, heads of units	introducing innovation management;
2	Improving the system of personnel training and retraining	During the year	Heads of units	developing a lifelong learning system
3	Expansion of material incentives forms	first quarter	Heads of units	introducing rewards (by initiative, personal contribution to the production process, development and implementation of new equipment and technology), participation in distribution of the received economic effect and profit, bonuses.
4	Increasing the role of intangible incentives	During the year	General director, heads of units	implementing social programmes and differentiated motivational priorities (based on the definition of personnel individual needs and motives)
5	Creating favourable socio-psychological conditions:	During the year	Heads of units	atmosphere of promoting professional self-development and self-realization, strategy of corporate culture, career advancement

Continuation of Table 1.

1	2	3	4	5
6	Motivation for the corporate culture development	During the year	Heads of units	taking measures to feel a sense of belonging to the company, participation in making important decisions; organizing holidays and special events for employees; annual vouchers for employees to sanatoriums, medical institutions and health resorts; providing personnel with the opportunity to participate in conferences at the regional and national levels; motivating employees who offer new solutions to business problems.
7	It is important for the manager to call the employees, ask how they are doing and whether they need help with something. At ZOOM video conferences, the manager should also pay attention to the mood of the colleagues and listen to what they are saying.	During the year	Heads of units	Creating an atmosphere of trust and strengthening the team online, when it becomes difficult to quickly identify a labour trouble, because constant contact with the employee is interrupted.
8	Creative managerial decisions development	During the year	Heads of units	Increasing the importance of the employees' creative participation is associated with the need to find non-standard solutions, new ideas for development.
9	Hybrid work format	During the year	Heads of units	An innovative model of work organization, in which employees spend part of their time in the company office, and the other part remotely. This format allows to combine the advantages of both models: the opportunity to meet and chat with colleagues, and the rest of the time to work from home.
10	Decentralizing management and decision making	During the year	Heads of units	The new technologies development and the global social changes associated with the epidemic situation in the country and the world are giving the office space new meaning. Work processes, company structures and management styles are changing. Transparency, security, mobility and communication are key words for modern work process scenarios.

Source: authors' own development

Summarizing the abovementioned it should be noted that improving the labour indicators and psychological climate in the team can be by means of organizational and educational measures aimed at effective correction and changes in the structure of labour motivation in individual groups of employees, as well as carrying out various measures to protect employees from the spread of coronavirus disease during the performance of their duties. It is advisable to remember that in difficult times the personnel needs less corporates, parties and trainings, but much more – care of the employer about physical, mental and emotional health. Especially in the context of the problem of occupational homing, the spread of which also acquires the pandemic nature. For example, during the pandemic, it is advisable for HR managers to call the company employees and ask about their health, remind them of the need to wear gloves and masks, and other safety measures.

Concern for the employees health care – this is where the pandemic changes in most companies began. And this is not about the insurance package, which has already become almost a standard bonus in official employment, but about the prompt response to the new epidemic and related quarantine restrictions. This is usually an opportunity to work online and have additional control over one's health.

The basic list of negative factors is expanded by the common fears of employees related to their financial condition, health of relatives and family situation. The employees cope with this in different ways: some are more prone to negative influences, some less – but everyone feels pressure [11-18].

Conclusions

As a result of the conducted study, it is possible to conclude that in the pandemic conditions, there have been more cases of bankruptcy and closure of economic entities, lower wages, uncertain future of both enterprises and personnel negatively affected the employees' morale and, as a result, their productivity.

In the conditions of limited financial resources enterprises of different branches of the Ukrainian economy are looking for ways to strengthen their enterprises competitiveness by increasing the personnel motivation to work and creating an effective system of personnel management. The enterprise employees, as the most important resource that influences its income, competitiveness and sustainable development, should be productive even in unstable environment.

Thus, improving the personnel motivation in the context of complex development of the personnel management model is an important economic task in the pandemic conditions, the solution of which will

increase the enterprise efficiency as a whole, since all the management spheres are closely interrelated and give the most complete return only on the basis of synergy.

Abstract

The realities of today make their adjustments both in our lives and in the work of enterprises, the management of which carries out all anti-epidemic measures imposed on the territory of a city of Ukraine in connection with the spread of COVID-19. All companies were forced to take measures to prevent the spread of infection, such as: cessation of any mass events at the company, control over the use of personal protective equipment, transfer of some or all employees to remote work, and so on. The problem of staff motivation became especially acute during the pandemic, when quarantine is introduced in the country, and many entrepreneurs are forced to limit the activities of their enterprises. Improving the system of personnel motivation in enterprises is a priority, as one of the problems of personnel management is the rational use of the human factor, and this is possible only with an effective approach to the motivation system. Insufficient study, development, as well as debatability and the need to address some issues related to personnel management in a pandemic and the degree of their impact on the performance of enterprises, both in economics and in industrial practice, identified the need for further consideration and selection of basic areas of research.

The main methodological method of research is the system-structural approach, which allows the most effective organization of the search for the solution of the tasks. Also, methods of comparative, functional analysis, classification are used. Theoretical and methodological basis of work were theoretical positions and scientific principles, developed by domestic and foreign specialists in the field of improving personnel motivation at the enterprise in the condition of a pandemic.

An effective remuneration system is a guarantor of stability, reduces staff turnover, ensures high quality performance, promotes the involvement of highly qualified and experienced employees, and thus ensures the success of the enterprise in the strategic dimension. The factor that ensures such productivity is the motivation of work as a factor in improving productivity and productivity, increasing the efficiency of the accumulated labor potential. As the study of scientific literature shows, motivation is a set of conditions or motives that affect human behavior, directing its activities in the necessary direction for the organization, regulating labor intensity, labor costs, encouraging honesty, perseverance, diligence in achieving goals. In other words, it is the driving force that helps the employee to combine all his efforts and effectively perform his duties to achieve the goal.

The development of a system of motivation aimed at meeting the needs of employees can be created according to what they consider important, it can create more favorable conditions for achieving the goals of the organization. Due to the fact that the object of incentives are workers of different categories, it is necessary to take into account the difference in their incentives. For young people, career growth and success in life are important. Employees before retirement have strong motives to increase their efficiency, recognition of their authority, values, necessity for the company and so on. For people whose financial situation is quite prosperous, moral motives can be much more important than material ones. Such employees attach great importance to the content of work, they enjoy the work and the results achieved. The difficult financial situation determines the predominance of material motives over moral motives. Therefore, the ability to distinguish the needs of employees is the basis for the formation of active behavior of employees and achieve the main goal of the company – profit maximization.

The key areas of motivation of enterprise staff in a pandemic are proposed, which require not only other approaches than in pre-pandemic times, but also empathy, care and attention to mental health, which will retain highly qualified employees in the context of increasing competitiveness in uncertainty.

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